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*Claudia Wiepcke and Ewald Mittelstädt***AMBIGUITY TOLERANCE – LEARNING HOW TO DEAL WITH UNCERTAINTY BY EXPERIMENTATION (PROTOTYPING)**

Educational policy of the state at the macro level and schools at the micro level are increasingly confronted with questions as to which key competences have to be developed in order to enable graduates of all levels to cope independently with a great variety of challenges in different life situations. One of the possible solutions could be provided by entrepreneurial education. The paper deals with entrepreneurial education, its principles and approaches that can be used beyond traditional business programmes to train students to cope efficiently with all types of social and professional challenges.

Entrepreneurial education is viewed in the paper as not limited to acquisition of knowledge and competences which are required for a successful start-up process and business management. It is a bundle of principles, decision-making logic and problem-solving techniques that everyone can access to a certain degree. These principles and techniques presented and substantiated in the paper can be applied in any sphere of life and professional activities. Entrepreneurship education empowers students in all circumstances to be more creative, opportunity-orientated, proactive and innovative, i.e. to become entrepreneurs. Young people who don't intend to become self-employed also benefit from such kind of education because it increases their participation, e.g. through higher employability. Entrepreneurial skills are highly valued by employers: it is people possessing entrepreneurial skills who help companies to become and stay innovative. As uncertainty has become a feature of the modern world, ability to deal with it is a most demanded skill education is supposed to develop and is known as the psychological construct of ambiguity tolerance.

Key words: student, entrepreneurial education, experiment.

Випке Клаудія, Міттельштедт Евальд. Толерантність до невизначеності. Як за допомогою експериментування навчитися діяти в ситуаціях невизначеності

Стаття присвячена підприємницькій освіті та тим педагогічним рішенням, які можуть бути використані освітніми інституціями різних рівнів поза її межами для того, аби навчити випускників самостійно справлятися

з різноманітними життєвими та професійними викликами.

Вживаючи термін «підприємницька освіта», автори мають на увазі весь комплекс освітніх підходів, стратегій та технологій, спрямованих на пробудження у людині підприємницького світогляду, формування та удосконалення таких підприємницьких навичок, як прийняття рішень, володіння технологіями вирішення проблем, що можуть бути корисними в різних сферах життя або професійної діяльності.

Підприємницька освіта дає змогу студентам у будь-якій ситуації бути креативними, знаходити можливості, діяти про активно та інноваційно, покращує їх перспективи знайти своє місце на ринку праці. Толерантність до ситуації невизначеності, вміння діяти ефективно в нестабільних, невизначених умовах – одна з найважливіших компетентностей, яку підприємницька освіта успішно формує та розвиває через ряд освітніх технологій, що розкриті в статті. Наприклад, технологія моделювання (створення прототипів) в курсі «Design Thinking». В рамках курсу студенти вчаться вирішувати проблеми в невизначених ситуаціях за допомогою експерименту: створюють прототипи, випробовують та удосконалюють їх. Таким чином підприємницька освіта сприяє особистісному розвитку та формуванню сучасних компетентностей студентів всіх рівнів і спеціалізацій.

Ключові слова: студент, підприємницька освіта, експеримент.

Винке Клаудиа, Миттельштедт Эвальд. Толерантность к неопределенности. Как с помощью экспериментов научиться действовать в ситуациях неопределенности.

Статья посвящена предпринимательскому образованию и тем педагогическим решениям, которые могут быть использованы образовательными учреждениями различных уровней за ее пределами для того, чтобы научить выпускников самостоятельно справляться с различными жизненными и профессиональными вызовами.

Употребляя термин «предпринимательское образование», авторы имеют в виду весь комплекс образовательных подходов, стратегий и технологий, направленных на пробуждение в человеке предпринимательского мировоззрения, формирования и совершенствования таких предпринимательских навыков, как принятие решений, владение технологиями решения проблем, которые могут быть полезными в различных сферах жизни или профессиональной деятельности.

Предпринимательское образование позволяет студентам в любой ситуации быть креативными, находить возможности, проактивно и инновационно

действовать, улучшает их перспективы найти свое место на рынке труда. Толерантность к ситуации неопределенности, умение действовать эффективно в нестабильных, неопределенных условиях – одна из важнейших компетенций, которую предпринимательское образование успешно формирует и развивает через ряд образовательных технологий, раскрыты в статье. Например, технология моделирования (создание прототипов) в курсе «Design Thinking». В рамках курса студенты учатся решать проблемы в неопределенных ситуациях с помощью эксперимента: создают прототипы, испытывают и совершенствуют их. Таким образом, предпринимательское образование способствует личностному развитию и формированию современных компетентностей студентов всех уровней и специализаций.

Ключевые слова: студент, предпринимательское образование, опыт.

Introduction

The 17 goals of Agenda 2030 for sustainable development (such as sustainable consumption and production, devising measures for climate protection set by the Federal Ministry for economic Cooperation and Development in Germany (BMZ) made it clear that we face many challenges both globally and nationally. The solution to these problems cannot be achieved by using the same approaches as those that have led to these problems. Education is the main vehicle for developing new solutions. Educational policy at the macro level and schools at the micro level are increasingly confronted with questions as to which key competences should be developed in order to cope independently with a great variety of challenges in different life situations. For this reason, the European Commission has suggested the promotion of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial education in several key documents since 2003 (see European Commission 2016: 36).

But what is entrepreneurial education? Entrepreneurial education is a transfer of knowledge and competences which are required for a successful start-up process and business management to students. In a broader sense, Entrepreneurship Education refers to all educational measures aimed at awakening in students of entrepreneurial attitudes and skills (see Wiepcke 2012, 290). Entrepreneurship Education is a set of principles, decision-making logic and techniques that everyone can acquire to a certain degree. Entrepreneurship education empowers students in all cases to be more creative, opportunity-orientated, proactive and innovative, i.e. to become

successful entrepreneurs. Young people who don't become self-employed will also benefit from Entrepreneurship education because will broaden their options, e.g. through higher employability, and will help companies to be more innovative. But how does innovative thinking work in a world that is becoming more ambiguous and uncertain? One possible approach is the so-called „blue ocean strategy“.

The Blue-Ocean-Strategy

The blue ocean strategy is intended for dealing with disruptive improvements of products or ideas for products. Disruption refers to a process in which an existing business model or market is replaced or

Attributes	Red Ocean activities	Blue Ocean activities
Competition	There is strong competition in the market, which determines the strategy of making entrepreneurial decisions. The strong focus on competition means that companies remain in the Red Ocean. They focus on competition and do not focus enough on customer benefits.	The market, where competition is fierce, is avoided. Companies focus on the benefits for their customers. As a result, all the facts relevant to competition in the industry are called into question.
Industry structure	Start-ups are based on the given structure of the industry and strategic planning starts with a structural analysis of the industry.	It is assumed that companies with their own 'right' strategy can change the industry structures to their advantage and create a new market.
Strategic Creativity	Creativity and innovation are regarded as irrelevant. For this reason, strategic planning focuses on securing competitiveness in existing markets.	Innovation can be systematically associated with benefits through creativity, so that industry boundaries can be restructured.
Demand	Companies try to increase their market share by using existing customers and gaining new ones from the same sector.	Companies look after non-customers in order to tap into and exploit new demand.

displaced by innovations. The blue ocean strategy divides markets into red oceans and blue oceans. In the chart below the most important features of decision making by means of the two strategies are presented and distinguished from each other.

In summary, it can be said that a part of the Blue Ocean is future markets in which competition isn't relevant for some time. The focus is on developing innovative benefits for customers in new market spaces. This way blue ocean products achieve differentiation (unique selling points), are initially low on competition and bring high profits (see Kim/Mauborgne2015).

Since the blue ocean strategy refers to future market spaces, decisions are made under the conditions of uncertainty. Entrepreneurs are encouraged to cope with uncertain and unpredictable situations. The decision-making logic of the blue ocean strategy neglects the plannable element (unlike the red ocean strategy) and focuses on the pragmatically feasible. The scientific interest in dealing with uncertainty has also formed its way to initial education and is to be known as the psychological construct of ambiguity tolerance (see Mittelstädt 2017).

Ambiguity tolerance – dealing with uncertainty

Ambiguity tolerance (uncertainty tolerance) means that people can deal with contradictory, unstructured, open and ambiguous situations. In general, it enables people to cope with the unpredictability of life. Such people can deal better with complex, ambiguous and/ or non-transparent tasks that cannot be solved by means of existing action strategies than people with weak ambiguity tolerance. Entrepreneurs usually have a higher degree of ambiguity tolerance than other groups (Bijedic 2013, 229). Because of that, it is one of the key competences for entrepreneurs to develop. With the help of experimental way of learning, such as the Marshmallow Challenge, the ambiguity tolerance of the students can be strengthened.

The Marshmallow Challenge

The Marshmallow Challenge (also known as the Spaghetti Tower) is an entertaining and motivating exercise that encourages students to experiment. Each team (3-5 people) gets 1 meter of string, 1 meter of tape, marshmallow, 20 spaghetti and a pair of scissors. The task is to build a tower as high as possible with these tools within the period of 18 minutes.

The team with the highest marshmallow on the top of the table wins. The teams' approach to planning and implementation should be assessed, evaluated and reflected upon (see Uebernickel et al. 2015,194).

Wujec (2010) examined the success rate of different teams. The highest towers are built by kindergarten children with an average height of 75 cm. Top managers build towers with an average height of 60 cm. The worst towers are built by economics students with an average height of 25 cm. Wujec explains the different success rates by the different approaches used. While children do not discuss how to do the task, but immediately start to build, try out building strategies straight away, repair and use broken spaghetti again, so in the end they construct stable and high towers. Business students, on the other hand, first discuss building plans and look for perfect solutions before getting down to business. The discussion prior to starting the building costs time. If you put the marshmallow on top at the end of the 18 minutes period, the tower will collapse and there will be no time for another attempt. The children's strategy is also called 'rapid prototyping'.

Testing assumptions with prototyping

The production of prototypes emerged within the framework of Design Thinking (see Mittelstädt/Wiepcke2018). In producing prototypes within the framework of business idea development, new concepts are not discussed long and theoretically, but are designed in the form of prototypes and quickly tested in practice. The thoughtfully developed idea of is transformed into a model that can be viewed, touched and transferred (see Freudenthaler-Mayrhofer/Sposato 2017, 209). The goal of the prototypes is to test them in practice. The target group gives feedback on the strengths and weaknesses so that new insights can be gained. The assumptions made can thus be confirmed or disproven on the market every week or month in the form of a new version.

Learning how to deal with uncertainty by experimentation

The experiments on the Marshmallow Challenge with children and business administration students show that children do not take a planning approach when building the Spaghetti Tower and thus build the highest and most creative towers. They face the uncertain situation by immediately starting to build (create a first prototype), trying (test assumptions) and improving (improve the prototype step by step). Children use rapid

prototyping, which is important for implementing a blue ocean strategy. Personality and competence development of students can be influenced by experimentation. Learning by discovering and action-orientation allows them to apply short decision-making processes as well as experiencing their limitations. The Marshmallow Challenge requires learners to develop the ability to recognize the demands placed on them and to take advantage of new ways of approaching them. This enables them to apply the structures learned to various economic situations as entrepreneurial strategies (see Schlusser/ Schuhen 2011 ,60).

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